

LINGUOCULTURAL ASPECT OF TRANSLATING “SUYUNCHI” INTO ENGLISH

Rustam Maxsumov Maxamadiyevich

Assistant teacher at Denau Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy

maxsumovrustam4@gmail.com

Abstract: This article studies the linguocultural challenges inherent in translating the Uzbek film "Suyunchi" into English. "Suyunchi" summarizes a complex blend of linguistic, cultural, and contextual variations that pose significant obstacles for translators. Through an analysis of various translation strategies and cultural implications, this study aims to shed light on the difficulties of generating "Suyunchi" into English while preserving its original meaning and cultural essence.

Keywords: translation, linguocultural, Suyunchi, uzbek and english, cultural variations, context, strategy.

It is one of the most difficult cases to convey national coloring. Owing to the translation very important literary works were able to appear in many other countries and became available for people speaking other languages. The translation helps mutual knowing and peoples' enrichment. National coloring must be reflected adequately in the translation.⁷⁰

The difficulties encountered in translation are primarily linked to conveying the national character of a particular work. The more vividly it portrays national life and characteristic situations, the more challenging it becomes for the translator to find appropriate functional and figurative means. Consequently, it is insufficient to merely convey realias and social nuances to capture the essence of the national character during translation. This can only be achieved if the translator can adeptly encapsulate the diverse forms of national character present in the creative works of various authors. National coloring is not an accessory to the work but rather a fundamental component that enriches the overall structure of the piece. In the process of analyzing the film "Suyunchi", we were convinced that there are scenes that reflect the uniqueness of the Uzbek national culture. We can see that each scene of the film consists of a style of speech that has a specific meaning and linguistic significance.

⁷⁰ Матасов Р.А. Перевод кино/видео материалов: лингвокультурологические и дидактические аспекты: диссертация. – М. МГУ, 2009.- 211 с.

We can prove these concepts on the basis of the following scenes:

Table 1

Uzbek concepts	English version
Anzirat buvining qishloqni aylanib chiqish saxnasi;	Anzirat grandmother's scene around the village;
Shaharlik shifokor bilan suxbatlashishi;	Conversation with the city doctor;
Otasini shifoxonaga ko'rish uchun bormagan farzand;	A child who did not go to the hospital to see his father;
Kelilining ko'ngli uchun farzandini uyidan haydagan ona;	A mother who kicked her child out of the house for the sake of her daughter-in-law;
Qishloqdagi noxaqlik uchun do'konchini koyigan ayol;	A woman who scolded a shopkeeper for injustice in the village;
Nabirasi uchun sovchilikka borgan buvi;	Grandmother who went matchmaking for her grandson;
Qishloqdoshlari uchun ko'prik qurdirgan general kampir;	An old general who built a bridge for her villagers;
Nabiralari sindirgan oynalar uchun haq to'lagan adolatparvar inson;	A fair man who paid for the broken windows of his grandchildren;
Shifoxonadan qochgan matonatli ayol;	A strong woman who escaped from the hospital;

Each scene has a specific linguocultural meaning. For example, through the scene of Grandmother Anzirat's tour of the village, we can see that the Uzbek people are not indifferent to the lives of their compatriots, the region in which they live and what is happening there.

In the scene of the conversation with the city doctor, Anzirat's grandmother scolds the doctor for locking the door, and she says to the doctor, "Why did you lock this door? Why would a thief break into your house?" From these sentences we can see the Uzbek people's trust in people and the relationship between the villagers.

Anzirat buvi: "Holmat, buz qulfni"

Shifokor: "Voy nima qilayapsiz-ey?"

Anzirat buvi: "O'pkangni bos, men shu yerda 75 yildan beri yashayman, hali birovni bir narsasi yo'qolganini bilmayman"

In the scene of a child who does not go to see his father in the hospital, Anzirat's grandmother and her friends try to raise a child who does not go to see their father in the hospital. The benefits of their efforts are touching. The boy goes with a bowl to get a message from his father. The concepts of bowls and glasses in this scene also represent our nationality. That is, in our people, tea is drunk in a cup, which is a sign of respect and nationalism.

“Choy ichishga piyolasi ham yo’g’a, stakonda choy ichyabdi”

A mother who evicted her child for the sake of her daughter-in-law, in this scene we can see the kindness and justice typical of Uzbek mothers-in-law. Anzirat's grandmother drives her child Sheramat out of the house because of her son's idleness and her daughter-in-law's tears. Let's focus on the following dialogue in this scene:

Anzirat buvi: Voy aqli odam-ey, menga uyat bo’larkanmi, o’nta bolani otasi bo’laturib ertadan kechgacha koptokni ketidan allakamni itiday lo’killab yurgan senga uyat bo’lmas ekan, menga uyat bo’lar emushmi?

Shermat: Shunaqami? Ho’p, bo’pti, qaytanga menga yaxshi, men erkin qushman hoxlagan tomonimga uchib ketaman.

Here we can see why the mother drove her child away. When Anzirat's grandmother says, "Alikamni itiday lo’killab" she means that her son is idle.

In the scene where a woman scolds a shopkeeper for injustice in the village, Anzirat grandmother and her friends go to Gaybulla, a shopkeeper, and accuse her of eating someone's rights by injuring the villagers:

Anzirat buvi: “Qishloq ahli sendan juda ham norozi. Qaytimini bermas emushsan”

G’aybulla: “Nima? Kimdan urub qolibman, a? Ko’zingiz bilan ko’rdingizmi o’zi?”

Anzirat buvi: “Afsus vaqtim yo’qda bo’lmasam adabingni berardim”

G’aybulla: “Ey osmon qo’lingizda bo’lsa tashlab yuboring”

From the above example, it can be seen that Anzirat grandmother is not indifferent not only to her family's situation, but also to the life of her neighbors.

Translating "Suyunchi" into English presents a formidable task due to its rich cultural connotations deeply rooted in Uzbek society. Various translation strategies may be employed, ranging from direct translation to cultural adaptation, each with its own set of advantages and limitations. However, regardless of the approach taken, it is essential for translators to remain sensitive to the linguistic and cultural variations lied within "Suyunchi" to ensure an accurate and culturally resonant rendition in English. This study underscores the importance of understanding the linguocultural

complexities involved in translation, particularly when dealing with words that carry significant cultural significance like "Suyunchi".

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